

Mass Spectrometry of Transition Metal η -Complexes. Part—VII: A Study of the Behaviour of Some Ruthenocene Derivatives[†]

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The mass spectral fragmentation of $(\eta\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{Ru}(\eta\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5\text{COR})$ ($R = \text{CH}_3, \text{Ph}$) (I, II) and $(\eta\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5\text{COCH}_3)_2\text{Ru}(\eta\text{-C}_5\text{H}_5\text{COCH}_3)$ (III) has been examined and compared with that of the ferrocene analogues. The higher metal-ligand bond strengths in the ruthenocene derivatives are reflected in much more extensive fragmentation of the metal-bound ligands compared to the behaviour of the ferrocenes. The ion, $(\text{M-CH}_3)^+$ from (III) shows an unusual loss of two CO groups in a single step, a process believed to be under thermodynamic control and leading to $[(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{Ru}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)]^+$.

THE mass spectral behaviour of ferrocene derivatives has been the subject of extensive study and much of this work has been reviewed¹. However, there has been no such studies on the ruthenocene analogues and only three studies have been reported on ruthenocene itself^{2,3,4}. Of particular interest is the study of Müller and D'Or³ which showed that 8.3% of the total metal-containing ion current of ruthenocene consists of ions of the type MC_2H_5^+ and MC_3H_7^+ , arising via successive loss of C_2 units from the molecular ion, compared to 1.1% for ferrocene. Furthermore, 9.5% of total metal-containing ion current of ruthenocene consists of ions of the type MC_4H_9^+ , MC_3H_7^+ , MC_2H_5^+ and MCH_3^+ , arising principally by fragmentation of MC_5H_9^+ , compared to 6.2% for ferrocene. The percentages of $(\text{Metal})^+$ are 13.3% for ferrocene and 1.8% for ruthenocene. These small, but significant, differences are in accord with slightly higher $\text{M-C}_5\text{H}_5$ bond dissociation energies in the ruthenium compound^{1,3,4}. We were interested to see if these differences would also manifest themselves in the mass spectra of substituted ruthenocenes and report here the behaviour of monoacetyl- and monobenzoyl-ruthenocene (I and II) and 1,1'-diacetyl-ruthenocene (III).

Results and Discussion

The spectrum of I is listed in Table 1 and is to be compared with that of monoacetylferrocene (IV) which has been previously reported⁵, but which was redetermined in this work (Table 2). Metastable peaks confirm only four fragmentations in IV. These are $\text{M}^+ \rightarrow [\text{M-CH}_3]^+$, $[\text{M-CH}_3]^+ \rightarrow [\text{M-CH}_3\text{CO}]^+$, $\text{M}^+ \rightarrow [\text{M-CH}_3\text{CO}]^+$ and $[(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{Fe}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)]^+ \rightarrow [\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{C}_5\text{H}_5]^+$. The fragmentation of I (Table 1) is supported by only two metastable peaks which confirm the first two of these fragmentations.

Two additional fragmentations of the molecular ion of I are observed over those of IV. These are loss of CH_2CO yielding $[(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{Ru}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)]^+$ and

TABLE 1—MASS SPECTRUM OF MONOACETYL-RUTHENOCENE (I)

m/z [†]	Rel. Abd. (%)	I/ΣI (%) [*]	Assignment
274	100	42	$(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{Ru}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{COCH}_3)^+$
254	21	9	$(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{Ru}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{CO})^+$
245	1.5	1	$\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{Ru}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)^+$
232	5	2	$(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{Ru}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)^+$
231	32	14	$(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{Ru}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)^+$
205	14	6	$(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{Ru}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)^+$
191	1	0.5	$(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)_2\text{Ru}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)^+$
180	1	0.5	$\text{Ru C}_5\text{H}_5^+$
179	4	2	$\text{Ru}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)^+$
167	16	7	$\text{Ru}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)^+$
154	4	2	$\text{Ru}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)^+$
153	1	0.5	$\text{Ru}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)^+$
141	6	2.5	$\text{Ru}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)^+$
140	5	2	$\text{Ru}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)^+$
139	7	3	$\text{Ru}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)^+$
130	1	0.5	$\text{Ru}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)^+$
129	2	1	$\text{Ru}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)^+$
128	1	0.5	$\text{Ru}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)^+$
127	1	0.5	$\text{Ru}(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5)^+$
114	8	4	RuC^+
102	4	2	Ru^+
92	2		$\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{CO}^+$
78	0.7		C_5H_5^+
77	1		C_5H_5^+
65	1.5		C_5H_5^+
64	2		C_5H_5^+
63	3		C_5H_5^+
52	1		C_5H_5^+
51	1.5		C_5H_5^+
50	1		C_5H_5^+
43	14		CH_2CO^+
39	7		C_5H_5^+
Metastable ions			m/z 244.8 274 → 259
			m/z 206.0 259 → 231

[†] Based on ¹⁰⁰Ru

^{*} Metal-containing ions only. All percentages rounded to the nearest 0.5%.

Dedicated to Professor A. K. Dey on the occasion of his 60th Birthday.

[†] Part VI, R. Davis, M. L. Webb, D. E. Millington and V. Parr, *Org. Mass Spectrom.*, 1979, 14, 289.

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TABLE 2—MASS SPECTRUM OF MONOACETYLFERROCENE (IV)

m/z	Rel. Abd. (%)	I/ΣI(%)*	Assignment
228	100	20	(C ₅ H ₅)Fe(C ₅ H ₄ COCH ₃) ⁺
213	17	3	(C ₅ H ₅)Fe(C ₅ H ₄ CO) ⁺
185	83	17	(C ₅ H ₅)Fe(C ₅ H ₄) ⁺
163	14	3	Fe(C ₅ H ₄ COCH ₃) ⁺
129	77	15	(C ₅ H ₅ ·C ₅ H ₄) ⁺
121	60	12	Fe(C ₅ H ₄) ⁺
95	13	3	Fe(C ₅ H ₅) ⁺
94	19	4	Fe(C ₅ H ₄) ⁺
81	21	4	Fe(C ₅ H) ⁺
71	25	5	Fe(CH ₃) ⁺
56	69	14	Fe ⁺
43	13	—	CH ₃ CO ⁺
39	16	—	C ₅ H ₄

* Metal-containing ions only.

Metastable ions m/z 199.0 228 → 213
 m/z 160.7 213 → 185
 m/z 150.1 228 → 185
 m/z 90.0 185 → 129

the unusual, although weak, loss of HCO. The product of this later reaction can be written in a number of ways, of which we chose [(C₅H₅)Ru(C₅H₄)]⁺, despite the fact that this involves a massive reorganisation of the ligand. We are encouraged to do this by the observation of the ions [Ru(C₅H₅)]⁺, [Ru(C₅H₄)]⁺, [C₅H₅]⁺ and [C₅H₄]⁺ as well as other expected fragments from these ions.

As with ruthenocene, the increase in metal-ligand bond strength in I over IV leads to 77% of metal-containing ions in the former containing greater than five carbon atoms, compared to 40% in IV. 23% of the metal containing ions in I contain five or less carbon atoms compared to 46% in IV and the (Metal)⁺ ion accounts for 2% of this ion current in I, but 14% in IV.

A number of other differences are noteworthy. Firstly, while IV shows formation of both [(C₅H₅)Fe]⁺ and [(C₅H₄COCH₃)Fe]⁺, only the former is observed for I suggesting that the difference between the metal-ligand bond strengths in I is much greater than that in IV. IV also shows a prominent fragmentation, [(C₅H₅)Fe(C₅H₄)]⁺ → [C₅H₅·C₅H₄]⁺ + Fe which is completely absent in I. Furthermore, no CH₃-transfer to the metal appears to occur in I although this is observed for IV. The ion [RuC]⁺ is observed and although there is no metastable ion to confirm its genesis, fragmentation of [Ru(C₅H₅)]⁺ by loss of C₅H₄ would seem an obvious route. Other steps involving C₅H₄ loss are common in the spectrum of I.

A comparison of the behaviour of II and monobenzoylferrocene (V) shows a similar pattern to that established for the monoacetyl derivatives. The fragmentation of V has been reported by others⁶ and is similar to that of IV except that the ion [(C₅H₅)Fe(C₅H₄)]⁺ formed by loss of C₅H₅CO⁺ is the most intense metal-containing fragment ion. In the case of the ruthenocene derivative (Table 3), the fragmentations M⁺ → (M-CO)⁺, M⁺ → (M-C₅H₅)⁺ and M⁺ → (M-C₅H₄CO)⁺ are supported by metastable peaks. As observed above, II also forms the ion

[Ru(C₅H₅)]⁺ but not [Ru(C₅H₄COCH₃)]⁺. Fragment ions formed by phenyl transfer to the metal atom [(C₅H₅)Ru(C₅H₄)(C₆H₅)]⁺ and [(C₅H₅)Ru(C₆H₅)]⁺ are observed.

TABLE 3—MASS SPECTRUM OF MONOBENZOYL RUTHENOCENE (II)

m/z ⁺	Rel. Abd. (%)	I/ΣI(Mo)*	Assignment
336	100	33	(C ₅ H ₅)Ru(C ₅ H ₄ COPh) ⁺
308	18	6	(C ₅ H ₅)Ru(C ₅ H ₄)Ph ⁺
306	17	6	(C ₅ H ₅)Ru(C ₅ H ₄) ⁺
259	24	8	(C ₅ H ₅)Ru(C ₅ H ₄ CO) ⁺
244	20	7	(C ₅ H ₅)RuPh ⁺
231	24	8	(C ₅ H ₅)Ru(C ₅ H ₄) ⁺
205	12	4	(C ₅ H ₅)Ru(C ₅ H ₄) ⁺
203	17	6	(C ₅ H ₅)Ru(C ₅ H) ⁺
167	18	6	(C ₅ H ₅)Ru ⁺
154	7	2	(C ₅ H ₅)Ru ⁺
141	18	6	(C ₅ H ₅)Ru ⁺
139	20	7	(C ₅ H ₄)Ru ⁺
105	21		C ₅ H ₅ PhCO ⁺
102	8	3	Ru ⁺
77	42		C ₅ H ₅ ⁺
65	17		C ₅ H ₄ ⁺
64	16		C ₅ H ₄ ⁺
63	25		C ₅ H ₅ ⁺
51	42		C ₅ H ₄ ⁺
50	29		C ₅ H ₅ ⁺
39	33		C ₅ H ₄ ⁺

Metastable ions m/z 282.3 336 → 308
 m/z 199.6 336 → 259
 m/z 177.2 336 → 244

⁺ Based on ¹⁰⁰Ru

* Metal-containing ions only. All percentages rounded to the nearest 1.0 %.

71% of total metal-containing ion current of II contains more than five of the ten original cyclopentadienyl carbon atoms and 28% contain five or less carbon atoms. These figures are similar to those observed for I, but not dissimilar to those of V (73% and 27%, respectively). However, only 3% of metal-containing ion current consists of Ru⁺ ions in II, whereas 13% of that of V consists of Fe⁺.

The mass spectrum of 1,1'-diacetylferrocene (VI) has also been examined in detail previously⁶. The main decomposition routes of the molecular ion, as evidenced by the observed metastable ions are M⁺ → (M-CH₃)⁺, M⁺ → (M-CH₃CO)⁺, (M-CH₃)⁺ → (M-CH₃-2CO)⁺ and (M-CH₃CO)⁺ → (M-CH₃-2CO)⁺ of which the loss of two CO groups in a single step is the most unusual. This behaviour has been observed in the fragmentation of some metal carbonyl complexes⁷. However, it is without precedent in the fragmentation of organic ketones, although it has been observed in the case of some ketone dimers⁸.

In the case of III, metastable ions confirm the fragmentation route, M⁺ → (M-CH₃)⁺ → (M-CH₃-2CO)⁺ → [(C₅H₅)]⁺. Thus the single step loss of two CO groups occurs with this molecule also. We propose that the driving force for this unusual fragmentation is formation of [(C₅H₅)Ru(C₅H₄)]⁺ which must again involve a massive reorganisation of the organic ligands, but which is under thermodynamic control. The other fragmentations of III are all of low abundance (Table 4) and are broadly

in accord with those observed for I. Again, 75% of the total metal-containing ion current contains greater than five cyclopentadienyl ring carbon atoms and 25% contain five or less. The figures for VI are 62% and 38%, respectively.

Thus, in summary, this preliminary study has demonstrated the rich variety of mass spectral fragmentations observed in the spectra of ruthenocene derivatives and further work is in progress in an effort to systematise this behaviour.

TABLE 4—MASS SPECTRUM OF 1,1-DIACETYLRUTHENOCENE (III)

m/z*	Rel. Abd. (%)	I/ΣI (%)*	Assignment
316	90	19	(C ₅ H ₄ COCH ₃)Ru(C ₅ H ₄ COCH ₃) ⁺ †
301	55	12	(C ₅ H ₄ COCH ₃)Ru(C ₅ H ₄ CO)
274	5	1	(C ₅ H ₄ COCH ₃)Ru(C ₅ H ₅) ⁺ †
259	4	1	(C ₅ H ₄ CO)Ru(C ₅ H ₅) ⁺
245	100	21	(C ₅ H ₅)Ru(C ₅ H ₅) ⁺
231	8	2	(C ₅ H ₅)Ru(C ₅ H ₄) ⁺
229	9	2	(C ₅ H ₅)Ru(C ₅ H ₃) ⁺
217	8	2	(C ₅ H ₅)Ru(C ₅ H ₂) ⁺
205	10	2	(C ₅ H ₅)Ru(C ₅ H ₁) ⁺
204	10	2	(C ₅ H ₄)Ru(C ₅ H) ⁺
191	8	2	(C ₅ H ₄)Ru(C ₅ H) ⁺
180	15	3	Ru(C ₅ H ₅) ⁺ †
179	16	3	Ru(C ₅ H ₄) ⁺
178	15	3	Ru(C ₅ H ₃) ⁺
167	50	11	Ru(C ₅ H ₂) ⁺
154	8	2	Ru(C ₅ H ₁) ⁺
153	7	2	Ru(C ₄ H ₄) ⁺
139	9	2	Ru(C ₄ H ₃) ⁺
137	11	2	Ru(C ₄ H) ⁺
114	14	3	RuC ⁺
102	12	2	Ru ⁺
78	5		C ₅ H ₅ ⁺
77	3		C ₅ H ₄ ⁺
65	7		C ₅ H ₃ ⁺
64	9		C ₅ H ₂ ⁺
63	13		C ₅ H ₁ ⁺
43	65		CH ₃ CO ⁺
39	14		C ₅ H ₅ ⁺

Metastable ions m/z 286.7 316 → 301
 199.4 301 → 245
 113.8 245 → 167

* Based on ¹⁰⁰Ru

* Metal-containing ions only. All percentages rounded to nearest 1.0 %.

Experimental

Ruthenocene was prepared by the method of Pertici *et al.*⁹. Mono- and diacetyl ruthenocene are prepared by the method of Hofler and Schlögl¹⁰. Monobenzoylruthenocene was prepared by a method exactly analogous to that of the mono-acetyl derivative. All gave satisfactory analytical data, nmr and infrared spectra.

Mass spectra were recorded on an AEI M.S.9. operating at 7 eV and 100 μA trap current and a source temperature of 50°.

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